

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) KAE_BZFP

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: KAE_BZFP

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0165 Å

Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=32.7902 (14) b=15.5418 (6) c=26.4018 (10)

 alpha=90 beta=102.694 (4) gamma=90

Temperature: 293 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	13126.0 (9)	13126.0 (9)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C15 H10 O6, 2 (C13 H9 N O)	4 (C15 H10 O6), 8 (C13 H9 N O)
Sum formula	C41 H28 N2 O8	C164 H112 N8 O32
Mr	676.65	2706.61
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.370	1.370
Z	16	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.790	0.790
F000	5632.0	5632.0
F000'	5650.38	
h, k, lmax	41, 19, 33	41, 18, 33
Nref	27704	26239
Tmin, Tmax	0.827, 0.888	0.756, 1.000
Tmin'	0.802	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.756 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.947

Theta(max)= 76.806

R(reflections)= 0.1634(10986)

wR2(reflections)=
0.4545(26239)

S = 1.026

Npar= 1846

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT082_ALERT_2_B	High R1 Value	0.16	Report
PLAT084_ALERT_3_B	High wR2 Value (i.e. > 0.25)	0.45	Report
PLAT340_ALERT_3_B	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.01645	Ang.

Alert level C

PLAT026_ALERT_3_C	Ratio Observed / Unique Reflections (too) Low ..	42%	Check
PLAT041_ALERT_1_C	Calc. and Reported SumFormula Strings Differ		Please Check
	Calc: C41 H28 N2 O8		
	Rep.: C164 H112 N8 O32		
PLAT042_ALERT_1_C	Calc. and Reported MoietyFormula Strings Differ		Please Check
	Calc: C15 H10 O6, 2(C13 H9 N O)		
	Rep.: 4(C15 H10 O6), 8(C13 H9 N O)		
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C9A --C10A .	0.16	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C2B --C3B .	0.16	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C11B --C16B .	0.18	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C2C --C3C .	0.20	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C11C --C16C .	0.21	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C162 --C172 .	0.18	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C126 --C136 .	0.23	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C146 --C196 .	0.16	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C166 --C176 .	0.20	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C147 --C157 .	0.17	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C167 --C177 .	0.19	Ang.
PLAT241_ALERT_2_C	High MainResAtom Ueq as Compared to Neighbours	O115	Check
PLAT241_ALERT_2_C	High MainResAtom Ueq as Compared to Neighbours	C155	Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low MainResAtom Ueq as Compared to Neighbours	C11C	Check
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd 1)	2.3	Note
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd 2)	2.5	Note
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd 4)	2.2	Note
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd 10)	2.1	Note
PLAT334_ALERT_2_C	Small <C-C> Benzene Dist. C145 -C195 .	1.37	Ang.
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	46.242	Check
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	6.609	Check
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	3.218	Check
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	2.177	Check
PLAT910_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min) [Deg]=	3.43	Note
	1 0 0, 1 1 0, 2 0 0, 0 1 1, -1 0 2,		
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	245	Report
	0 18 0, 1 18 0, 2 18 0, 8 18 0, 9 18 0, 10 0 0,		
	11 0 0, 15 11 0, -13 15 1, -12 15 1, -11 15 1, -9 18 1,		
	-5 18 1, -4 18 1, -3 17 1, -3 18 1, -2 18 1, -1 18 1,		

0 8 1, 0 18 1, 2 17 1, 3 8 1, 8 18 1, 9 18 1,
15 5 1, 16 5 1, 16 15 1, 17 5 1, -30 0 2, -13 15 2,

(215 More NOT listed: see .ckf listing file)

PLAT975_ALERT_2_C Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 1.09Ang From O7A . 0.47 eA-3
PLAT975_ALERT_2_C Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.94Ang From O4C . 0.43 eA-3

Alert level G

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms 16 Report
H4PA H3A H5A H7A H4PB H3B H5B H7B
H4PC H3C H5C H7C H3D H4PD H5D H7D
PLAT045_ALERT_1_G Calculated and Reported Z Differ by a Factor ... 4 Check
PLAT083_ALERT_2_G SHELXL Second Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large 90.00 Why ?
PLAT199_ALERT_1_G Reported _cell_measurement_temperature (K) 293 Check
PLAT200_ALERT_1_G Reported _diffrn_ambient_temperature (K) 293 Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O111 . 105.2 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O112 . 106.6 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O113 . 104.9 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O114 . 106.3 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O115 . 106.3 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O116 . 105.7 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O117 . 105.7 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O118 . 106.5 Degree
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G Short Inter X...Y Contact O4C ..C228 . 3.00 Ang.
x,l+y,z = 1_565 Check
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G Short Inter X...Y Contact O4D ..C226 . 2.98 Ang.
x,y,z = 1_555 Check
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 8 Note
O4PA H4PA O4PB H4PB O4PC H4PC O4PD H4PD
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G Centre of Gravity not Within Unit-Cell: Resd. # 5 Note
C13 H9 N O
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G Centre of Gravity not Within Unit-Cell: Resd. # 11 Note
C13 H9 N O
PLAT802_ALERT_4_G CIF Input Record(s) with more than 80 Characters 1 Info
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL 2019/3 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 1082 Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G Number of HKL-OMIT Records in Embedded .res File 5 Note
0 8 1, 3 8 1, 0 5 5, -8 11 11, -8 11 13,
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity 1.9 Low
PLAT965_ALERT_2_G The SHELXL WEIGHT Optimisation has not Converged Please Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 4.016 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 11.32 or SHELX Weight 44.27 Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 0 Info
PLAT992_ALERT_5_G Repd & Actual _reflns_number_gt Values Differ by 4 Check

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
3 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
30 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
27 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

5 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
25 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
10 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
17 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
3 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

PLATON version of 23/04/2026; check.def file version of 30/03/2026

duplicate check

No duplication found

Datablock KAE_BZFP - ellipsoid plot

